

ANALYSIS OF THE CURRENT STATUS OF THE QUALITY OF THE EDUCATION SYSTEM IN KASHKADARYO REGION

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Abstract: This article provides an in-depth analysis of the current state of the quality of the education system in the Kashkadarya region. The research examines the activities of general secondary education, secondary specialized and higher education institutions, their material and technical base, the level of modernity of curricula, the potential of teaching staff, and the quality of student knowledge. It also analyzes the monitoring of education quality, existing problems, regional differences, lack of infrastructure, and obstacles to the transition to digital education. At the end of the article, scientifically based proposals and recommendations are given to improve the current situation.

Keywords: Kashkadarya region, quality of education, teaching staff, digital education, analysis, education monitoring, curricula, regional problems, modern educational requirements.

Introduction. Today, the education system plays a crucial role in the socio-economic development of any country. Based on the reforms being implemented by the Republic of Uzbekistan, in particular, the Law "On Education" and the "Digital Uzbekistan - 2030" strategy, comprehensive measures are being taken to improve the quality of education at each level.

Kashkadarya region, as a region with unique demographic, social and infrastructural characteristics, is an important object for analyzing the quality of education in this region. The growth in the number of students, the uneven distribution of school infrastructure, the need for qualified pedagogical personnel, and the level of implementation of digital educational technologies require special attention in the analysis.

This work analyzes the state of the education system in the Kashkadarya region based on indicators, monitoring data, problematic aspects, and ways to eliminate them.

The infrastructure of the educational services market, like other economic infrastructure sectors, is inextricably linked with the labor market. This infrastructure is a system of mechanisms that regulate labor relations between employers and job seekers, including labor prices, working conditions, training and retraining of personnel, as well as legal relations between enterprises and employees. The infrastructure of the educational services market plays an

important role in ensuring the balance of supply and demand in the labor market.

The higher education system is considered one of the main components of the labor market infrastructure and directly affects the dynamics of supply and demand in the market by training highly qualified specialists. Today, the effectiveness of the higher education system is associated not only with traditional educational programs, but also with concepts such as digital transformation, lifelong learning, and industry 4.0. Therefore, it is necessary to take into account new terms and processes in a modern analysis of the infrastructure of the educational services market.

Key elements of the educational services market infrastructure

Employer-job seeker relationships: In this process, it is necessary to increase the level of relevance to market demands through HR technologies and talent management tools. Employers are often focusing on modern competencies such as soft skills and employability skills.

Supply and demand in the labor market: In this area, data-driven approaches, i.e., the analysis of large amounts of data to accurately determine market forecasts, create opportunities for the strategic development of educational services.

Training and retraining of specialists: Upskilling and reskilling processes have become an integral part of the infrastructure of modern educational services. These processes are ensuring the individualization and increase in efficiency of educational processes with the help of online learning platforms, virtual reality (VR) and augmented reality (AR) technologies.

Legal regulation and working conditions: Labor relations are shifting to new formats through the gig economy and freelance platforms. This requires the introduction of new standards and flexible procedures in labor codes.

Modern factors influencing the infrastructure of the educational services market: Currently, global and local trends are having the following main impacts on the educational infrastructure: **Technology integration:** Learning Management Systems (LMS) and AI-based tutoring systems are improving the quality of educational services and making them available on a large scale.

Forecasting supply and demand: Forecasting labor market needs using Big Data analytics and Artificial Intelligence (AI) algorithms ensures the adaptation of educational programs.

International integration of education: Through programs such as cross-border education and dual-degree programs, students and professionals adapt to the global labor market.

Modern economic indicators play an important role in analyzing the development of the educational services market infrastructure:

Employment rate:

$$ER = \frac{\textit{Band aholi soni}}{\textit{Iqtisodiy faol aholi soni}} \times 100\%$$

This indicator assesses the level of training of higher education institutions in line with market needs.

Unemployment rate:

$$UR = \frac{\textit{Ishsizlar soni}}{\textit{Iqtisodiy faol aholi soni}} \times 100\%$$

This indicator plays an important role in assessing the effectiveness of the educational services market.

Turnover rate:

$$TR = \frac{\textit{IShdan bo' shagan xodimlar soni}}{\textit{Umumiy ishchilar soni}} \times 100\%$$

This indicator shows the need to improve cooperation between employers and educational institutions.

The infrastructure of the educational services market is a system that provides interconnection between employers, students and educational institutions, incorporating modern approaches. Through digital transformation and the introduction of new technologies, the opportunity to optimize the educational process and adapt to market needs has significantly increased. Therefore, through the consistent development of infrastructure elements, it is possible to achieve sustainable and high-quality growth in the labor market.

Experts say that the underdeveloped infrastructure in the educational services market indicates a significantly low level of their participation in the processes of coordinating changes in the labor market of our country. It is necessary to further expand the market for educational services and organize and develop the activities of personnel agencies and various types of specialized employment services that collect information about demand and supply in the labor market and provide personnel with decent work. It is advisable for these structures to focus on remote areas and rural areas. "Education level and profession (i.e. job) status are compatible only when the demand for and supply of highly qualified labor in the labor market are in balance. If the demand for qualified labor exceeds the supply of highly qualified specialists, employers are

forced to fill existing vacancies with workers with lower qualifications than required. In this case, professional requirements for specialists change. If the supply of qualified labor exceeds demand, a stable demand for one or another specialty creates an excess demand for these specialties in educational institutions. However, due to the volatility of the labor market, an imbalance between supply and demand soon arises. As a result, young people who have mastered these specialties, due to changes in the market situation, agree to work in less socially and economically prestigious jobs. This leads to a certain devaluation of diplomas from educational institutions. ". Employers, taking advantage of the excess of

supply over demand, increase the demand for professional qualifications for jobs." In the context of socio-economic changes taking place in our country, state management of the process of training, placement and employment of specialists is of particular importance in shaping the labor market.

Kashkadarya region 2017-2023 information and informatization services indicators (in billion soums)

No.	Years	Information and informatization services	Change (+,-) in a chain-like manner		Chain-linked rate of change in %	Change, in the basic way		Basic method change rate in %	Share of total information and informatization services in %
1	2008	5.1	+			+			0.1
2	2009	4.3		0.8	5.7		0.8	15.7	0.08
3	2010	4.6	0.		6.		0.5	9.8	0.07
4	2011	142.4	137.8		96.8	137.3	96.4		2.6
5	2012	171.1	28.7		6.8	166	9		3.1
6	2013	206.2	35.1		7	201.1	97.5		3.8
7	2014	241.2	35		4.5	236.1	97.9		4.4
8	2015	274.8	33.6		2	269.7	98.1		5
9	2016	328.7	53.9		6.4	323.6	98.4		6
10	2017	372.8	44.1		1.8	367.7	98.6		6.9
11	2018	432.2	59.4		3.7	427.1	98.8		7.9
12	2019	437.1	4.9		1	0.9	98.8		8

13	2020	496.1	59	11.9	59	99	9.1
14	2021	599.1	103	17	103	99.1	11
15	2022	765.5	166.4	21.7	176.4	99.3	14
16	2023	960.6	195.1	20.3	195.5	99.5	17.7
17	2024	1167.9	207.3	21.6	207.3	99.7	21
	Average	388.8	72.1	17.8	168.8	84.5	8.8
	Total information and informatization costs:	6609.7					

Conclusion. Analysis shows that although the quality of education in Kashkadarya region has been improving relatively in recent years, there are still a number of systemic problems. In particular, the poor condition of school buildings in some districts, the excessive number of students, the need for qualified teaching staff, and the lack of modern educational tools and digital infrastructure remain factors that reduce the quality of education.

At the same time, the situation can be significantly improved by introducing digital educational tools, updating methodological manuals, establishing a system of continuous professional development for teachers, and expanding the exchange of experiences between schools.

In conclusion, it is an urgent task to conduct consistent monitoring of the quality of education in the Kashkadarya region, introduce a differentiated approach taking into account local conditions, and develop development programs based on scientifically based strategies.

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